

Exploring alternative approaches to improve the convergence pattern in solving the coupled-cluster equations

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ABSTRACT

The perturbational parameter λ formally appearing in the coupled-cluster (CC) and perturbation theory (PT) frameworks is included explicitly in the Hamiltonian and the CC formalism. Using the Møller–Plesset (MP) partitioning, properties of the resulting λ -dependent amplitude functions are discussed. Truncating the cluster expansion at singles and doubles (CCSD), we use these properties and knowledge of the CCSD amplitudes at $|\lambda| < 1$ values to estimate the CCSD amplitudes without solving the relevant equations at $\lambda = 1$ (corresponding to the original, physical problem). This extrapolation scheme is explored, with emphasis on convergence improvement of CC iterations. The approximate amplitudes generated by this procedure are used as the starting point for the CCSD iterations, an alternative to the first order MP (MP1) set. Numerical examples are presented which show that the technique combined with the direct inversion in the iterative subspace (DIIS) method is especially helpful in situations where the standard CCSD iterations converge slowly or not at all. We report cases where starting from MP1, the solution process has an unfavourable convergence pattern even with DIIS applied, while the amplitudes generated by our method provide a much better starting point, overcoming the divergence issues of the original sequence.

KEYWORDS

coupled-cluster equations, amplitude function, extrapolation, convergence properties

1. Introduction

Since its original formulation, coupled-cluster (CC) theory [1–4] has become a standard tool in *ab initio* electronic structure calculations. In order to tackle a broad range of problems, over the years a large family of CC methodologies with various levels of sophistication have been developed. The exponential parametrization of the Ansatz offers the advantage of size-extensivity, and even if the cluster operator is truncated at a certain level, some effects of higher excitations are also incorporated. By including excitations of higher rank, one can establish a hierarchy of CC models with (in theory) increasing accuracy. The corresponding amplitude equations are nonlinear, and solving them efficiently often poses a challenge. Due to nonlinearity, they require an iterative solution process. In many situations (e.g. quasi-degeneracy, breaking of multiple bonds)

This paper is dedicated to Professor Péter G. Szalay on the occasion of his 60th birthday.

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the single-reference (SR) theory is meaningful only if higher (triple [5, 6], quadruple [7] etc.) excitations are also incorporated in the Ansatz [8, 9]. An alternative is presented by the multireference (MR) framework, which comes with its own set of challenges [10]. Our focus however remains on the SR-CC formalism.

Solution of the relevant equations is hindered by several factors: the large amount of amplitudes (which grows quickly if one goes beyond double excitations), the computational effort required to evaluate the amplitude equations, and convergence issues in the iterative process. Closely related to the latter, the number of iterations needed to reach a certain accuracy is also an important component. Efficiency can be improved via introduction of appropriate intermediate quantities [7, 11], or parallelization [12, 13].

Difficulties with convergence may arise e.g. in (quasi)degenerate situations, when an amplitude is large, i.e., the wavefunction is not dominated by the reference determinant [9, 14], (similarly to the breakdown of single-reference perturbation theory (SRPT), which is not surprising given the connection of the two formalisms [1, 15]). Even if that is not the case, there could be complications with the iterative process if the fixed point of the iteration (i.e. the solution) is not a stable fixed point. The *a posteriori* analysis of this phenomenon can be performed [16] by examining the Jacobian of the CC equations [17], but the problem of unfavourable convergence patterns remains.

To overcome these issues, different extrapolation techniques have been proposed, such as implementing the direct inversion in the iterative subspace (DIIS) method [18] in the CC framework [19], and the related reduced linear equation (RLE) approach [20, 21]. DIIS could further be improved by identifying an optimal set of trial vectors thus reducing the number of previous iterations needed for the extrapolation [22].

More recently, convergence acceleration was achieved by re-structuring the amplitude equations and following a different iteration pathway [23]. Further approaches involve the approximation of the Jacobian at a different level of theory [24] as well as using the Newton-Krylov method [25] to solve the nonlinear equations. These works typically deal with higher order CC models, going beyond singles and doubles (CCSD). Categorisation and identification of significant amplitudes either via machine learning or analytical derivations can also lead to convergence improvement [26, 27].

For CCSD, conventionally the first-order Møller–Plesset (MP) [28] amplitudes serve as the initial guess. In this paper, we keep the original iterative process, but follow a different route to initialize cluster amplitudes. Using the MP partitioning of the Hamiltonian, the perturbational parameter λ is included explicitly in the operator, resulting in λ -dependent amplitudes and CC equations. The amplitudes are treated as functions of the parameter λ , and their properties as such functions are inspected. We focus on the possibility of predicting the amplitudes at $\lambda = 1$ (corresponding to the original problem) based on knowing them at other, smaller values of λ . The advantage of this approach is the relatively fast convergence of CC calculations for small values of the parameter. This extrapolation scheme is explored, with emphasis on adequacy of the new guess and convergence improvement of CC iterations.

The paper is organized as follows. In Sec.2 the main idea of the theory is elaborated, and the details of the extrapolation are discussed. Computational details are briefly summarized in Sec.3. Finally, the technique outlined in Sec.2 is tested on the examples of Sec.4, restricting our investigations to CCSD.

2. Theory

2.1. Dependence on the perturbational parameter

A general single-reference (SR) CC wavefunction Ansatz has the expression

$$|\Psi_{\text{CC}}\rangle = e^{\hat{T}}|\Phi_0\rangle, \quad (1)$$

where $|\Phi_0\rangle$ is the reference determinant, while operator \hat{T} involves excitations with respect to $|\Phi_0\rangle$. In the following, p refers to an arbitrary spinorbital with corresponding creation and annihilation operators a_p^\dagger and a_p , while i, j, \dots denote occupied, a, b, \dots denote unoccupied spinorbitals in $|\Phi_0\rangle$, respectively. The cluster operator is given as

$$\hat{T} = \sum_{k \geq 1} \sum_{\substack{i_1 < \dots < i_k \\ a_1 < \dots < a_k}} t_{a_1 \dots a_k}^{i_1 \dots i_k} a_{a_1}^\dagger \dots a_{a_k}^\dagger a_{i_k} \dots a_{i_1} \equiv \sum_{k \geq 1} \sum_{\substack{i_1 < \dots < i_k \\ a_1 < \dots < a_k}} t_{a_1 \dots a_k}^{i_1 \dots i_k} \hat{a}_{i_1 \dots i_k}^{a_1 \dots a_k}. \quad (2)$$

The CC equations are derived by substituting Eq.(1) into the time-independent Schrödinger equation,

$$\hat{H}e^{\hat{T}}|\Phi_0\rangle = E_{\text{CC}}e^{\hat{T}}|\Phi_0\rangle. \quad (3)$$

With some rearrangement and by projecting with an excited state $|\Phi_{ij\dots}^{ab\dots}\rangle = \hat{a}_{ij\dots}^{ab\dots}|\Phi_0\rangle$, we obtain the well-known CC amplitude equations:

$$\langle \Phi_{ij\dots}^{ab\dots} | e^{-\hat{T}} \hat{H}_N e^{\hat{T}} \Phi_0 \rangle = 0. \quad (4)$$

These are nonlinear in the amplitudes, and as mentioned before, they are solved in an iterative fashion. For standard schemes, the solution process relies on the partitioning of the Hamiltonian as

$$\hat{H} = \hat{H}^{(0)} + \hat{W}, \quad (5)$$

where the zero-order Hamiltonian, $\hat{H}^{(0)}$ is derived from the Fockian:

$$\hat{H}^{(0)} = \sum_p f_p^p a_p^\dagger a_p. \quad (6)$$

In the above, f_p^p are the diagonal elements of the Fockian. In case of canonical orbitals, the operator of Eq.(6) is the zero-order MP Hamiltonian. If orbitals are non-canonical, Eq.(6) corresponds to a partitioning where the offdiagonal elements of the Fockian are part of the perturbation \hat{W} . While some of our observations hold for any diagonal $\hat{H}^{(0)}$, orbitals are assumed to be canonical so that comparison to MP results is meaningful. In the following, $|\Phi_0\rangle$ will denote the Hartree–Fock (HF) determinant.

During the iterative solution process the initial guess for the amplitudes, termed the first order contribution is based simply on the first order MP (MP1) amplitudes. The terminology becomes apparent if the perturbational parameter λ tuning the strength of the perturbation is not only formally, but explicitly included in the Hamiltonian as

$$\hat{H}(\lambda) = \hat{H}^{(0)} + \lambda \cdot \hat{W}, \quad (7)$$

since then the amplitudes, and consequently the CC wavefunction itself as well as the energy become functions of λ :

$$\hat{H}(\lambda)e^{\hat{T}(\lambda)}|\Phi_0\rangle = E_{CC}(\lambda)e^{\hat{T}(\lambda)}|\Phi_0\rangle, \quad (8)$$

or equivalently,

$$e^{-\hat{T}(\lambda)}\hat{H}(\lambda)_N e^{\hat{T}(\lambda)}|\Phi_0\rangle = \Delta E_{CC}(\lambda)|\Phi_0\rangle, \quad (9)$$

where $\hat{H}(\lambda)_N = \hat{H}(\lambda) - \langle\Phi_0|\hat{H}(\lambda)|\Phi_0\rangle$ and $\Delta E_{CC}(\lambda) = E_{CC}(\lambda) - \langle\Phi_0|\hat{H}(\lambda)|\Phi_0\rangle$. We refer to the latter as the ‘correlation energy’ even if $\lambda \neq 1$. Similarly, the amplitude equations become

$$\langle\Phi_{ij\dots}^{ab\dots}|e^{-\hat{T}(\lambda)}\hat{H}(\lambda)_N e^{\hat{T}(\lambda)}|\Phi_0\rangle = 0. \quad (10)$$

When expanding the amplitudes (collected in the array $\mathbf{t}(\lambda)$) in a Taylor series according to the powers of λ , the first non-vanishing contribution is at first order and matches the MP1 amplitudes, hence the nomenclature. In conventional approaches, however, the entire λ -dependence is only considered implicitly.

In this work, we keep the parameter λ explicitly in the working equations, and explore the properties of the arising $\mathbf{t}(\lambda)$ and $\Delta E_{CC}(\lambda)$ functions. Such an approach has already been investigated in the context of PT [29–33] but scarcely in the CC framework, despite their close connection.

For the $\lambda = 1$ (i.e., the physical) case, solution of Eq.(10) is proposed by separating the terms on the rhs. of Eq.(10) which contain the diagonal part of the Fockian, i.e.,

$$g_{ij\dots}^{ab\dots}(\hat{H}, \mathbf{t}) + (f_a^a + f_b^b + \dots)t_{ab\dots}^{ij\dots} - (f_i^i + f_j^j + \dots)t_{ab\dots}^{ij\dots} = 0, \quad (11)$$

which is rearranged as

$$t_{ab\dots}^{ij\dots} = \frac{g_{ij\dots}^{ab\dots}(\hat{H}, \mathbf{t})}{(f_i^i + f_j^j + \dots) - (f_a^a + f_b^b + \dots)}. \quad (12)$$

In the above, function $g_{ij\dots}^{ab\dots}$ collects all other terms of Eq.(10). If one sticks to the MP partitioning (or in the non-canonical case, to the zero-order Hamiltonian of Eq.(6)), then it can be easily shown that the λ -dependent amplitude equations, when rearranged, take the form

$$t_{a\dots}^{i\dots}(\lambda) = \lambda \cdot \frac{g_{i\dots}^{a\dots}(\hat{H}(1), \mathbf{t}(\lambda))}{(f_i^i + \dots) - (f_a^a + \dots)}. \quad (13)$$

For details we refer to Appendix A.

Comparing Eqs.(12) and (13), the iterative process is very easily modified formally: in each step, we use the previous (λ -dependent) amplitudes in *the same* expressions as for $\lambda = 1$, and multiply the obtained new amplitude by λ , until convergence is reached.

The λ -dependent CC equations (whether the expansion is truncated or not) in their original form (cf. Eq.(10)) possess the following properties:

- terms containing λ explicitly are linear in λ ,

- all of the equations are algebraic in $\mathbf{t}(\lambda)$, i.e., they contain products of nonnegative powers of the different $t_\nu(\lambda)$ amplitudes (where ν refers to some arbitrary excitation).

The first observation implies that coefficients in the algebraic equations (i.e., coefficients corresponding to certain amplitude products) are linear functions of λ . A set of such equations has solutions which are analytic almost everywhere (apart from some exceptional points) [29, 34].

Exploiting these properties provides a new approach to find the solution of the CC equations at $\lambda = 1$. Even if the CC procedure does not converge at $\lambda = 1$, for small values of $|\lambda|$, the iterations are expected to converge in few steps. Thus, for a range of values $\lambda \in [0, r]$ for some $0 < r < 1$, the functions $E(\lambda)$ and $\mathbf{t}(\lambda)$ can be constructed. Gaining knowledge about $E(\lambda)$ and $\mathbf{t}(\lambda)$ on $[0, r]$ allows one to take advantage of the above mentioned properties of these functions in order to estimate their values at $\lambda = 1$.

While CC iterations generally start from the MP1 values, the strategy outlined above permits one to have a different, preferably better starting point for the procedure. This could result in two things: on one hand, a better initial guess could speed up the iterative process in cases where it is already convergent, on the other hand, it can turn an originally divergent case to a convergent one. The examples presented in Sec. 4 explore these possibilities.

2.2. Extrapolation techniques

For a non-exceptional value λ_0 , an amplitude $t_\nu(\lambda)$ is a smooth function in the neighbourhood of it, i.e., locally, close to λ_0 , function $t_\nu(\lambda)$ can be approximated quite well by a polynomial. However, on a larger interval such as $[0, 1]$ a polynomial approximation of a certain order might be too crude. Based on previous experience from PT [35–37], similar arguments imply that squareroot-type functions may be better suited for the task.

Regardless of the explicit form of the extrapolating functions, there are two different strategies that can be followed: analysing and extrapolating each of the amplitudes either individually, or simultaneously. The former has the advantage that the computational effort is essentially proportional to the number of amplitudes. On the other hand, this approach may lead to an imbalance of the extrapolated t_1 and t_2 (and if used, the higher order) amplitudes. In the latter case, instead of treating the t 's separately, functions of the amplitudes are evaluated and assessed, taking into consideration that the exact amplitudes are not independent of each other. However, these functions need to be chosen so that recovering the actual t 's from them is efficiently achievable, otherwise the advantage of this technique is lost.

2.2.1. Individual extrapolation

By this technique we mean that for a certain amplitude t_ν , the function $t_\nu(\lambda)$ is evaluated at K different points, and then a specific type of function is fitted to these data. As mentioned before, a squareroot-type function similar to a quadratic Padé approximant [38–40] is expected to perform well, or at least significantly better than a polynomial or rational approximation. Therefore two types of extrapolating functions

were considered. The first is a more general $[M, M, M]$ -type Padé approximant, i.e.,

$$t_\nu(\lambda) \approx \frac{-q_M(\lambda) + \sqrt{q_M(\lambda)^2 - 4p_M(\lambda)r_M(\lambda)}}{2p_M(\lambda)}, \quad (14)$$

where p_M, q_M and r_M are polynomials of degree at most M . The parameters of the fitting are thus the coefficients of these polynomials. Note, that while the independent variable of p_M, q_M and r_M is λ , the polynomials obtained for different amplitudes are of course different, i.e., p_M, q_M, r_M depend on ν as well. We omit this from the notation. An alternative to Eq.(14) is to solve

$$p_M(\lambda) \cdot t_\nu(\lambda)^2 + q_M(\lambda) \cdot t_\nu(\lambda) + r_M(\lambda) = 0, \quad (15)$$

which yields a system of linear equations for the coefficients, as for each given value of λ , Eq.(15) is linear in these parameters (which are the unknown quantities in this scenario).

The second option tested is a special case of Eq.(14), obtained by requiring that $p_M(\lambda) \equiv 1$. While this is a less flexible parametrization, for the same M values it involves less unknown coefficients, implying that $t_\nu(\lambda)$ is required to be evaluated at fewer intermediate λ values.

2.2.2. Simultaneous extrapolation

We remark that imbalance is possibly brought by the independent treatment. This may be avoided if instead of extrapolating each t_ν separately, the estimation is performed on some combinations (functions) of the amplitudes, or other constraints are imposed.

An option is to assess some linear combinations of amplitudes, meaning that from the array of $\mathbf{t}(\lambda)$ amplitudes a new one is formed via some matrix \mathbf{A} , and the elements of $\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{t}(\lambda)$ are extrapolated to $\lambda = 1$. Getting the actual t 's back from the extrapolated functions essentially requires the inverse of \mathbf{A} to be calculated. As the dimension of \mathbf{A} corresponds to the number of amplitudes, this is only feasible if \mathbf{A} has a special structure, for which \mathbf{A}^{-1} can be expressed easily.

It could be argued that since the amplitude equations are nonlinear, using linear transformations is not justified. However, it is not an extreme option either, cf. applicability of different linearized coupled-cluster techniques [41–44] in certain situations. Nevertheless, the choice for nonlinear transformation (and combination) of amplitudes was also tested.

2.2.3. Technical details

As will be discussed in Sec. 4 in more detail, one needs fairly accurate values of the function $\mathbf{t}(\lambda)$ at intermediate λ values in order to obtain a good estimate at $\lambda = 1$. Furthermore, reasonable extrapolated values require a modest amount of such intermediate points. These two features turn out to be the bottleneck of this approach: accuracy requires more iterations, and evidently, increasing the number of intermediate values also increases the total number of necessary iterations. Without any further considerations, this could result in a situation where exploring the function $\mathbf{t}(\lambda)$ on an interval in appropriate detail is no longer favourable to simply starting the iteration at $\lambda = 1$ from the MP amplitudes.

In order to reduce the cost of the screening process, the following modifications were

considered.

- (1) Initial values for the inbetween λ values — usually with the exception of the first a points — are not derived from the MP amplitudes, rather they are generated based on the previous $\mathbf{t}(\lambda)$ values using our proposed method, and
- (2) the number of iterations performed for the intermediate λ 's is limited (resulting in not perfectly accurate $\mathbf{t}(\lambda)$ values).

It was found that the most successful approach in alleviating the issue of too many iterations was to combine these two. Therefore, unless noted otherwise, in the examples presented in Sec. 4, the following recipe was applied. The number of $\lambda < 1$ points used for the extrapolation was $a + b$, where for each of the first a values c iterations were carried out, starting from the MP guess, while for each of the latter b λ values, d iterations were performed, starting from the guess generated by our method based on the preceding λ values. Additionally, the fact $\mathbf{t}(0) = \mathbf{0}$ was also taken advantage of. It needs to be noted again, that the $\mathbf{t}(\lambda)$ values obtained this way may not be fully converged, i.e., the result is a slightly inaccurate screening of the $\mathbf{t}(\lambda)$ function on the interval $[0, r]$ (where r is equal to the largest intermediate $|\lambda|$ value). From the data collected this way, the guess for $\lambda = 1$ was generated using one of the extrapolation methods described in Secs. 2.2.1 and 2.2.2. Thus in this setup, the number of iterations performed to obtain our new guess is $a \cdot c + b \cdot d$.

2.3. Computational cost

Generally speaking, the extrapolation itself is much cheaper than one single CC iteration, since the number of operations is proportional to the number of amplitudes (which is trivial for the individual extrapolation of amplitudes and holds also for the simultaneous treatment provided that the transformations are chosen appropriately), and the number of ‘inbetween’ λ values used. The former is at least one order of magnitude smaller than the cost of a single CC iteration, while the latter is usually small (e.g., < 20), thus a bounded quantity (i.e., $\mathcal{O}(1)$). What one needs to keep in mind is that of course, in order to obtain $E(\lambda)$ and $\mathbf{T}(\lambda)$ for smaller λ values, CC iterations must be carried out. Although for smaller values of λ , there are less amplitudes which are nonzero (or are above a threshold), these iterations are still contributing to the overall computational effort. Therefore the overall cost is the same order of magnitude as that of a standard CC procedure. The difference lies in the number of iterations needed, and if that can be reduced, the efficiency can be increased.

3. Computational details

To test the proposed approach, the CCSD model was used in our applications. The λ -dependent CCSD equations and their evaluation were implemented in the DIRCCR12-OS program [45]. The discussed extrapolation techniques were carried out with the help of a standalone FORTRAN code. In each of the following applications, the restricted HF solution is used as the reference in CCSD, with canonical molecular orbitals. Furthermore, in these examples a CCSD solution process is considered to be converged when the energy difference of two consecutive iterations is below a certain threshold, which — unless noted otherwise — is $0.1 \mu E_h$. To track the iteration process, besides observing the CCSD correlation energy in each step, the residual norm is also monitored. We define the residual norm as the norm of the difference of two consecutive

amplitude vectors, i.e.,

$$r_n := \|\mathbf{t}_n - \mathbf{t}_{n-1}\| , \quad (16)$$

with n indicating the iteration step. Obviously, if $r_n = 0$ for some n , then $\mathbf{t}_n = \mathbf{t}_{n-1}$, meaning that \mathbf{t}_n satisfies Eqs.(11). We emphasize that in this framework ‘extrapolation’ is pertaining to two different concepts: one is the estimation of $\mathbf{t}(\lambda = 1)$ (denoted by $\tilde{\mathbf{t}}(1)$) based on the knowledge of $\mathbf{t}(\lambda)$ function for *other* (smaller) values of λ . The other is aiming at extracting a better approximation to $\mathbf{t}(\lambda = 1)$ based on other estimates to $\mathbf{t}(\lambda = 1)$, i.e., use vectors at *the same* $\lambda(= 1)$ value, e.g. by DIIS. In this work by ‘extrapolated amplitudes’ we refer to the former. Moreover, the two can be combined: by first screening $\mathbf{t}(\lambda)$ on an interval and proceeding as described in Sec. 2.2, we obtain an approximate set of amplitudes at $\lambda = 1$. Using this as the initial guess, we start the iterative process for $\lambda = 1$, during which extrapolation in the second sense may be performed.

4. Illustrative examples

4.1. Well-groundedness

This section aims at showing that our proposed method is indeed an adequate tool to approximate the amplitude vectors at $\lambda = 1$. To this end, we present an analytical and a numerical example.

4.1.1. H_2 in minimal basis

We examine the H_2 molecule in minimal (e.g. STO-3G) basis. Let us denote the two spatial orbitals by ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 , which are assumed to be canonical, i.e. the Fockian is diagonal. The closed-shell Hartree–Fock ground state is $|\Phi\rangle = 1_\alpha^+ 1_\beta^+ |\text{vac}\rangle$. CCSD is of course exact in this case. Due to symmetry, there are two distinct amplitudes, one corresponding to the single exciations $\hat{a}_{1_\alpha}^{2_\alpha}$ and $\hat{a}_{1_\beta}^{2_\beta}$, and one to the only possible double excitation ($\hat{a}_{1_\alpha 1_\beta}^{2_\alpha 2_\beta}$). We denote them by $t := t_2^1$ and $T := t_{22}^{11}$, respectively. After simplifications, the CCSD amplitude equation for t is given as [11]

$$(f_2^2 - f_1^1)t + (2v_{12}^{21} - v_{12}^{12})t + (v_{12}^{22} - v_{11}^{21})(T + t^2) = 0 , \quad (17)$$

where $v_{pq}^{rs} = [pq|rs]$ stands for the two-electron integrals. Again, due to symmetry, integrals v_{12}^{22} and v_{11}^{21} vanish, thus the CCSD equation for t reduces to

$$(f_2^2 - f_1^1)t + (2v_{12}^{21} - v_{12}^{12})t = 0 . \quad (18)$$

The λ -dependent equation then reads as

$$(f_2^2 - f_1^1)t + \lambda(2v_{12}^{21} - v_{12}^{12})t = 0 . \quad (19)$$

The above equation has a unique solution $t = 0$ whenever $\lambda \neq \frac{f_1^1 - f_2^2}{2v_{12}^{21} - v_{12}^{12}}$.

The CCSD equation for the doubly excited amplitude T is, after substitution of

$t = 0$

$$v_{22}^{11} + T(2f_2^2 - 2f_1^1) + T(v_{11}^{11} + v_{22}^{22} + 2v_{21}^{12} - 4v_{12}^{12}) - T^2 v_{22}^{11} = 0, \quad (20)$$

while its λ -dependent counterpart is

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda v_{22}^{11} + T(2f_2^2 - 2f_1^1) + T\lambda(v_{11}^{11} + v_{22}^{22} + 2v_{21}^{12} - 4v_{12}^{12}) - T^2 \lambda v_{22}^{11} &= 0 \\ \lambda c + T(b_1 + \lambda b_2) - T^2 \lambda a &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

with $a = c = v_{22}^{11}$, $b_1 = 2(f_2^2 - f_1^1)$ and $b_2 = v_{11}^{11} + v_{22}^{22} + 2v_{21}^{12} - 4v_{12}^{12}$. For nonzero λ 's, Eq.(21) is a quadratic equation in T with coefficients that are linear in λ . In fact, Eq.(15) with $M = 1$, $p_1(\lambda) = -\lambda a$, $q_1(\lambda) = b_1 + \lambda b_2$ and $r_1(\lambda) = \lambda c$ is identical to Eq.(21). That is, if we were to fit a $[1, 1, 1]$ quadratic Padé approximant to the values sampled from the $T(\lambda)$ function, we would not simply get an approximation to $T(\lambda)$ (and thus for $T(1)$) but would actually recover the $T(\lambda)$ function exactly. This reinforces the choice for quadratic Padé type approximants. Obviously, for larger systems the CCSD equations are more involved and cannot be brought to such a form. In those cases, Eq.(15) will truly be an estimation to the amplitudes.

4.1.2. HF

As a starting numerical example, we take the HF molecule in cc-pVQZ basis, with interatomic distance set to 4.0 bohr. We performed calculations at different λ values, tabulated in Table 1. For each λ , the starting point of the iteration was the (scaled) MP guess, and to accelerate convergence, DIIS was employed. The number of iterations (n_{it}) required to get converged energies is provided in Table 1. With the help of this system we show that the method described in Sec. 2 is indeed able to predict CCSD amplitudes at $\lambda = 1$. In this example, we focussed on this feature and were not yet concerned with efficiency. For this reason we aimed at accuracy, and required the CCSD correlation energies to be converged to nine digits.

Table 1. Number of iterations needed to reach 10^{-9} E_h accuracy in the CCSD correlation energy at different values of λ , for the HF molecule in cc-pVQZ basis.

λ	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0
n_{it}	5	8	9	11	12	16	19	23	32	32

Based on five of the above λ values (namely, $\lambda = 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$) with the additional information that $\mathbf{t}(\lambda = 0) = \mathbf{0}$, we employ the extrapolation techniques of Sec. 2.2 to obtain an estimate for $\mathbf{t}(\lambda = 1)$. The CCSD amplitudes were extrapolated individually. To assess accuracy, the same process was carried out for nine intermediate values (ranging from $\lambda = 0.0$ to 0.8 with a step size of 0.1) as well.

The amplitude vectors obtained via extrapolation from six and nine points are denoted by $\tilde{\mathbf{t}}_s(1)$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{t}}_n(1)$, respectively, which are compared to the exact amplitudes at $\lambda = 1$, i.e., $\mathbf{t}(1)$. Table 2 collects the squared norms of the extrapolated amplitude vectors as well as their error (compared to the exact data), and the estimate for the amplitude with largest absolute value. Both for the extrapolation based on six and on nine points, the nonlinear scheme performs worst. Extrapolating amplitudes either individually or their linear combinations yields similar results. Correlation energies calculated with the estimated amplitudes follow the same pattern. The exception is

the individually extrapolated set of amplitudes based on nine points, as they provide a very accurate energy. This is fortuitous, since the error of the $\tilde{\mathbf{t}}_n(1)$ vector is albeit small, but nonzero.

Table 2. Properties of the extrapolated CCSD amplitudes obtained by different extrapolation techniques. The test system is the HF molecule in cc-pVQZ basis. The squared norm of the exact CCSD amplitude vector is $\|\mathbf{t}(1)\|^2 = 3.1257 \cdot 10^{-1}$, and the exact amplitude with the largest absolute value is -0.4253 . The CCSD correlation energy is $-0.392449 E_h$.

extrapolated from 6 points				
extp. method	$\ \tilde{\mathbf{t}}_s(1)\ ^2$	$\ \tilde{\mathbf{t}}_s(1) - \mathbf{t}(1)\ ^2$	largest $ t $	$E_{\text{CCSD}}(\tilde{\mathbf{t}}_s) / E_h$
independently	$3.0580 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.4110 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-0.4173	-0.39080
linear comb.	$3.1023 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$2.5521 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-0.4173	-0.39368
nonlinear comb.	$3.3352 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$4.4690 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-0.4433	-0.39958

extrapolated from 9 points				
extp. method	$\ \tilde{\mathbf{t}}_n(1)\ ^2$	$\ \tilde{\mathbf{t}}_n(1) - \mathbf{t}(1)\ ^2$	largest $ t $	$E_{\text{CCSD}}(\tilde{\mathbf{t}}_n) / E_h$
independently	$3.1341 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$9.7228 \cdot 10^{-6}$	-0.4257	-0.39249
linear comb.	$3.1337 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.8089 \cdot 10^{-6}$	-0.4257	-0.39196
nonlinear comb.	$3.2152 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$7.1441 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-0.4311	-0.39560

Fig. 1 shows the amplitude with the largest absolute value (corresponding to the pair excitation from the lowest lying core orbital to the fifth virtual MO) as a function of λ . The exact amplitude (purple curve) as well as the two extrapolated curves (based on six and nine points, obtained with the linear combination technique of Sec. 2.2.2) are shown. The green curve corresponds to the estimation based on six intermediate λ values (green cross in Fig. 1), while the yellow curve is the extrapolation obtained based on nine points (three additional values indicated by yellow asterisks). Panel (a) depicts the whole $[0.0, 1.0]$ range, while panel (b) shows the tails of the curves. On the larger scale, the exact and 9-point based curves are indistinguishable. Based on panel (b), the two can be separated, with the inset showing the very close neighbourhood of $\lambda = 1.0$ ($[0.998, 1.000]$). The error of the extrapolation based on six points is ca. $8.03 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (2%), while the one based on nine points has an error of 0.1%.

Based on the norms of the amplitude vectors as well as Fig. 1, the approximation obtained from six intermediate points has ca. 98% accuracy, while including three additional points decreases the error by an order of magnitude.

The quality of the $\tilde{\mathbf{t}}(1)$ vectors highlights the power of the method outlined in Sec. 2.2. This tool is able to recover the $\mathbf{t}(\lambda)$ amplitude functions fairly accurately based on data at intermediate λ values. Of course, in this form it is not efficient, as in order to obtain the estimates, amplitudes corresponding to smaller lambda values had to be computed. For the nine ‘inbetween’ λ ’s, this required $5 + 8 + 9 + 11 + 12 + 16 + 19 + 23 = 103$ iterations, followed by 8 – 10 additional steps in the actual iterative procedure at $\lambda = 1$. In comparison, by starting from the MP1 amplitudes, only 20 steps are required to reach the same accuracy. Therefore the cost-reducing considerations discussed in Sec. 2.2.3 are indeed necessary.

4.2. N_2

The N_2 molecule with an increased interatomic distance is assessed next in cc-pVTZ [46] basis. The elongated bond length is taken to be 3.4 bohr. Although for the correct

Figure 1. The largest CCSD t_2 amplitude for the HF molecule in cc-pVQZ basis as a function of the perturbational parameter λ . Interatomic distance is 4.0 bohr.

description of the dissociation of the nitrogen molecule, higher excitations are also needed at larger distances [8, 47], we remain in the region of the potential curve where CCSD is still adequate.

Figure 2. Divergence of the CCSD energy for the N_2 molecule in cc-pVTZ basis in the absence of extrapolation techniques. The initial guess is based on the MP amplitudes. The interatomic distance is set to 3.4 bohr.

The standard iterative approach without any extrapolation is pathologically divergent, the correlation energy exhibiting an oscillatory tendency with increasing amplitude (cf. Fig. 2). As seen in Fig. 3, keeping the MP initial guess but employing DIIS considerably dampens the oscillations, however, no convergence is reached within 60 steps.

For comparison, a different initial guess was also tested. To obtain the new guess, we used the method described in Sec. 2.2.3, with parameters $a = 4$, $b = 7$, $c = 2$ and $d = 3$, i.e., preceding the iteration at $\lambda = 1.0$, 29 steps were carried out. Using these intermediate values, the extrapolation was performed simultaneously on linear combinations of the amplitudes (cf. Sec. 2.2.2). The functions applied in the process were of quadratic Padé type. With these starting amplitudes, the CCSD iterations converge in a similar pattern to that of the MP guess with DIIS, cf. Figs 3 and 4. Note, that on top of our extrapolated initial amplitudes, DIIS was also used. To emphasize

Figure 3. Convergence pattern of the CCSD energy for the N_2 molecule in cc-pVTZ basis. Starting point of the iteration is the MP guess, DIIS is used. For geometry, see Fig. 2.

that the new guess was obtained by performing altogether 29 iterations previously, the starting point of the curve in panel (a) of Fig. 4 is not 0, rather the x axis is shifted by 29.

Figure 4. Convergence pattern of the CCSD energy for the N_2 molecule in cc-pVTZ basis, with the initial guess generated by our method. DIIS is also used. The x axis is shifted by 29 to indicate the steps used to obtain the guess. For geometry, see Fig. 2.

The main difference of the two processes is their large-order behaviour. For the MP guess, six digit accuracy in the energy is reached after 68 steps, as can be seen in the second panel of Fig. 3. In comparison, with our extrapolated set of amplitudes, the same accuracy can be obtained after 20 iterations, which, combined with the 29 steps needed to generate it, yields a step count of 49 (panel (b) of Fig. 4). The juxtaposition of the two curves is depicted in panel (a) of Fig. 5. Six (and later seven) digit accuracy in the energy is reached sooner with the initial amplitudes provided by our approach (blue curve). The residual norm of the iterations, plotted in panel (b) of Fig. 5, reinforces this conclusion. It declines more rapidly with our guess, eventually going below that of the MP guess.

Figure 5. Comparison of the CCSD convergence for the N_2 molecule in cc-pVTZ basis, with the MP initial guess (green curve) and our extrapolated guess (blue curve). For geometry, see Fig. 2.

4.3. Cr_2

We performed CCSD calculations on the chromium dimer in cc-pVDZ basis [48], which is reportedly a tough problem even for DIIS: according to Ref. [25], in the presence of DIIS, CCSD iterations slowly converge in an oscillating pattern, while without any extrapolation technique, the results are divergent when starting from the MP1 amplitudes.

Our findings are similar: after a few steps, DIIS is switched on, which dampens the oscillations in the estimated correlation energy. The overall pattern seems to be that of convergence, with values oscillating around ca. $-0.9385 E_h$, cf. panel (a) of Fig. 6. However, even after 60 iterations, the amplitude of the oscillation does not get under $0.1 \text{ m}E_h$, as seen on panel (b) of Fig. 6. Allowing the iterations to go further does not change the picture.

Figure 6. Convergence pattern of the CCSD energy for the Cr_2 molecule in cc-pVDZ basis, when starting from the MP amplitudes. DIIS is employed. The interatomic distance is set to 1.7 \AA .

To overcome this issue, the technique outlined in Sec. 2.2.3 was applied to this

system, with parameters $a = 7$, $b = 8$ and $c = d = 6$. Thus to obtain the new, improved guess, 90 iterations were carried out preceding the calculation at $\lambda = 1.0$. Based on these inbetween values, the extrapolating function used was a quadratic Padé type approximant, applied to the amplitudes individually. The CCSD iterations with the initial amplitudes generated in this procedure provided a converging sequence. During the iterations, DIIS was also employed. Accuracy in energy up to five digits is established fairly quickly, as can be observed in Fig. 7. The x axis is shifted by 90 to emphasize that generating the initial guess for the iterative process required 90 additional steps.

Figure 7. Convergence pattern of the CCSD energy for the Cr_2 molecule in cc-pVDZ basis, when starting from the extrapolated amplitudes combined with DIIS. The x axis is shifted by 90 to indicate the steps used to obtain the guess.

Starting with our guess, the converged CCSD correlation energy is $-1.024842 E_h$, whereas when beginning with the MP guess, the energy oscillates around a different value, and is off by ca. 86 mE_h , indicating that those amplitudes are not close to the actual solution. This is also highlighted by the residual norms, which are plotted in Fig. 8. While for the MP guess, residual norm (green curve) quickly drops below 10^{-2} (not depicted in the figure, but after 18 steps), it essentially stays above 10^{-3} during the course of the iteration, signalling that the set of amplitudes is far from converged. On the other hand, with our initial guess, the residual norm (blue curve) falls below 10^{-4} after 29 steps (cf. $n = 119$), and decreases further. It needs to be noted that our extrapolated set of amplitudes is not accurate in itself, as indicated by the initial residual norm ($n = 90$ in Fig. 8), as well as its estimation for the correlation energy ($-1.065792 E_h$, with an error of ca. 41 mE_h). Still, employing our guess as a starting point, the CCSD iterations can follow a path to the correct amplitudes.

4.4. TiO_2

As a final example, we show CCSD results for the TiO_2 molecule. Geometry was taken from Ref. [49], and the aug-cc-pVTZ basis set [48, 50] was used. Convergence pattern of the correlation energy for the different initial guesses is shown in Fig. 9, the corresponding residual norms are plotted in Fig. 10. Similarly to the nitrogen molecule, if there is no extrapolation present, the MP amplitudes yield an oscillatory and divergent sequence (not plotted). If DIIS extrapolation is performed during the

Figure 8. Residual norm during CCSD iterations for the Cr_2 molecule.

iterations, we get a convergent sequence. The damping effect of DIIS is clearly visible in Fig. 9, as it is applied after the first six iterations. Convergence is still rather slow, however: five-digit accuracy of the energy is established in 32 steps, and meeting the convergence criteria needs 67 iterations.

Figure 9. Convergence pattern for the CCSD correlation energy for the TiO_2 molecule with different initial amplitude sets. Data for the extrapolated amplitude guess (blue curve) is shifted by 8 to indicate the steps required to obtain it. The unshifted curve (purple) is also shown. Basis set is aug-cc-pVTZ.

Our extrapolated set of amplitudes bring further improvement. In order to generate this guess, we applied the scheme of Sec. 2.2.3, with parameters $a = 5$, $b = 3$, and $c = d = 1$. This means that altogether 8 steps precede the start of the iterative process at $\lambda = 1$. Extrapolation of the amplitude functions was performed individually, with quadratic Padé type functions. The resulting energy sequence is shown in itself (purple curve) and with the 8 unit offset (blue) in Figs. 9 and 10. Our extrapolated amplitudes do not cure the problem of divergence by themselves: in the absence of other treatment, the resulting iterative sequence would still diverge. However, combined with DIIS, we get convergent results. Five digit accuracy is achieved after 20 iterations, and convergence criteria are met after 28 steps, which is nearly half as many steps as for the MP set, even with the 8-step offset. Panel (b) of Fig. 9 shows this (the curve for the extrapolated guess flattens out sooner).

Figure 10. Residual norm for different initial guesses during the iterative solution of the CCSD equations for the TiO_2 molecule in aug-cc-pVTZ basis.

The quality of our extrapolated amplitudes themselves can be better examined if we do not include the 8-step offset. The resulting purple curves (which are just back-shifted copies of the blue ones) correspond to this case. Compared to MP, our initial $\tilde{\mathbf{t}}(1)$ amplitudes possess favourable features. On one hand, the estimate for the correlation energy obtained by them is much more accurate than MP2 (cf. the $n = 0$ point of the purple and green curves in panel (a) of Fig. 9): its error is an order of magnitude less (6.5 mE_h vs. 70.5 mE_h). The residual norm of our initial guess is also two orders of magnitude less than that of the MP1 amplitudes.

5. Conclusions

Explicit inclusion of the perturbational parameter λ into the CC equations yields λ -dependent amplitude functions. We have shown that the governing equations get modified in a straightforward manner. These amplitude functions (and the ‘correlation energy function’ as well) possess properties (analyticity at most points) which allow us to predict them at $\lambda = 1$ without solving the CC equations at that point.

Screening of the amplitude functions on an interval permits us to extrapolate to the $\lambda = 1$ point. The associated cost is proportional to the number of amplitudes, therefore the overall cost is determined by the number of CC iterations performed during the screening process. The resulting estimation for the amplitude vector can be used in itself or as a starting point for subsequent CC iterations. If beginning with the MP1 amplitudes the solution process converges relatively quickly (e.g. in less than ca. 20 steps), our method will probably not improve upon that, since producing our guess requires a comparable amount of iterations. However, the results in Sec. 4 show that our technique combined with DIIS is successful in cases where the MP1 amplitudes even with DIIS yield divergent or slowly convergent sequences. The method presented in this paper could also be combined with convergence enhancing approaches other than DIIS as well.

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Disclosure statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

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Appendix A. The λ -dependent amplitude equations

We recall that the cluster operator has the form

$$\hat{T} = \sum_{k \geq 1} \sum_{\substack{i_1 < \dots < i_k \\ a_1 < \dots < a_k}} t_{a_1 \dots a_k}^{i_1 \dots i_k} \hat{a}_{i_1 \dots i_k}^{a_1 \dots a_k} \equiv \sum_{k \geq 1} \sum_{I_k, A_k} t_{A_k}^{I_k} \hat{a}_{I_k}^{A_k}, \quad (\text{A1})$$

where $I_k \equiv i_1 \dots i_k$ and $A_k \equiv a_1 \dots a_k$ multiindices have been introduced to shorten the notation. The amplitude equations (cf. Eq.(4))

$$\langle \Phi_{i \dots}^{a \dots} | e^{-\hat{T}} \hat{H} e^{\hat{T}} \Phi_0 \rangle = 0. \quad (\text{A2})$$

with $\Phi_{i \dots}^{a \dots} = \hat{a}_{i \dots}^{a \dots} |\Phi_0\rangle$ are partitioned as

$$g_{i \dots}^{a \dots}(\hat{H}, \mathbf{t}) + (f_a^a + \dots) t_{a \dots}^{i \dots} - (f_i^i + \dots) t_{a \dots}^{i \dots} = 0. \quad (\text{A3})$$

We now shift the focus to the λ -dependent case, i.e., we assume that the Hamiltonian has the form of Eq.(7). Formally, the amplitude equations for $\mathbf{t}(\lambda)$ have the structure

$$\langle \Phi_{i \dots}^{a \dots} | e^{-\hat{T}(\lambda)} \hat{H}(\lambda) e^{\hat{T}(\lambda)} \Phi_0 \rangle = 0. \quad (\text{A4})$$

Using the fact that

$$\hat{H}(\lambda) = \lambda \cdot \hat{H}(1) + (1 - \lambda) \cdot \hat{H}^{(0)} , \quad (\text{A5})$$

we obtain

$$\lambda \cdot \langle \Phi_{i\dots}^{a\dots} | e^{-\hat{T}(\lambda)} \hat{H}(1) e^{\hat{T}(\lambda)} \Phi_0 \rangle + (1 - \lambda) \cdot \langle \Phi_{i\dots}^{a\dots} | e^{-\hat{T}(\lambda)} \hat{H}^{(0)} e^{\hat{T}(\lambda)} \Phi_0 \rangle = 0 . \quad (\text{A6})$$

This form of the λ -dependent amplitude equations is very convenient as the first term, $\langle \Phi_{i\dots}^{a\dots} | e^{-\hat{T}(\lambda)} \hat{H}(1) e^{\hat{T}(\lambda)} \Phi_0 \rangle$ is easily evaluated as (cf. Eq.(11))

$$g_{i\dots}^{a\dots}(\hat{H}(1), \mathbf{t}(\lambda)) + \{ (f_a^a + \dots) - (f_i^i + \dots) \} \cdot t_{a\dots}^{i\dots}(\lambda) , \quad (\text{A7})$$

whereas under certain circumstances, the second term, $\langle \Phi_{i\dots}^{a\dots} | e^{-\hat{T}(\lambda)} \hat{H}^{(0)} e^{\hat{T}(\lambda)} \Phi_0 \rangle$ is also readily available. Namely, if the zero-order Hamiltonian can be expressed as in Eq.(6) (e.g. if we use the Møller–Plesset partitioning with canonical orbitals), then the Baker–Campbell–Hausdorff [51–53] expansion of $e^{-\hat{T}(\lambda)} \hat{H}^{(0)} e^{\hat{T}(\lambda)}$ contains only two terms, without any truncation. This is due to the fact that the $\hat{H}^{(0)}$ of Eq.(6) has a very simple commutator with an excitation operator $\hat{a}_{I_k}^{A_k}$. In particular, for $I_k \equiv i_1 \dots i_k$ and $A_k \equiv a_1 \dots a_k$, one has

$$\begin{aligned} [\hat{H}^{(0)}, \hat{a}_{I_k}^{A_k}] &= \{ f_{A_k} - f_{I_k} \} \hat{a}_{I_k}^{A_k} \\ &= \{ (f_{a_1}^{a_1} + \dots + f_{a_k}^{a_k}) - (f_{i_1}^{i_1} + \dots + f_{i_k}^{i_k}) \} \hat{a}_{I_k}^{A_k} . \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A8})$$

From the above it follows that $[[\hat{H}^{(0)}, \hat{T}(\lambda)], \hat{T}(\lambda)] = 0$, consequently,

$$\begin{aligned} e^{-\hat{T}(\lambda)} \hat{H}^{(0)} e^{\hat{T}(\lambda)} &= \hat{H}^{(0)} + [\hat{H}^{(0)}, \hat{T}(\lambda)] \\ &= \hat{H}^{(0)} + \sum_{k \geq 1} \sum_{I_k, A_k} \{ f_{A_k} - f_{I_k} \} t_{A_k}^{I_k}(\lambda) \hat{a}_{I_k}^{A_k} . \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A9})$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \Phi_{i\dots}^{a\dots} | e^{-\hat{T}(\lambda)} \hat{H}^{(0)} e^{\hat{T}(\lambda)} \Phi_0 \rangle &= \langle \Phi_{i\dots}^{a\dots} | \hat{H}^{(0)} | \Phi_0 \rangle + \langle \Phi_{i\dots}^{a\dots} | \sum_{k \geq 1} \sum_{I_k, A_k} \{ f_{A_k} - f_{I_k} \} t_{A_k}^{I_k}(\lambda) \hat{a}_{I_k}^{A_k} | \Phi_0 \rangle \\ &= 0 + \{ (f_a^a + \dots) - (f_i^i + \dots) \} t_{a\dots}^{i\dots}(\lambda) . \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A10})$$

Combining Eqs.(A6), (A7) and (A10) yields

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \lambda \cdot \left(g_{i\dots}^{a\dots}(\hat{H}(1), \mathbf{t}(\lambda)) + \{ (f_a^a + \dots) - (f_i^i + \dots) \} t_{a\dots}^{i\dots}(\lambda) \right) \\ &\quad + (1 - \lambda) \cdot \{ (f_a^a + \dots) - (f_i^i + \dots) \} t_{a\dots}^{i\dots}(\lambda) \\ &= \lambda \cdot g_{i\dots}^{a\dots}(\hat{H}(1), \mathbf{t}(\lambda)) + (\lambda + 1 - \lambda) \cdot \{ (f_a^a + \dots) - (f_i^i + \dots) \} t_{a\dots}^{i\dots}(\lambda) \\ &= \lambda \cdot g_{i\dots}^{a\dots}(\hat{H}(1), \mathbf{t}(\lambda)) + \{ (f_a^a + \dots) - (f_i^i + \dots) \} t_{a\dots}^{i\dots}(\lambda) , \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A11})$$

which can be rearranged to give

$$t_{i\dots}^{a\dots}(\lambda) = \lambda \cdot \frac{g_{i\dots}^{a\dots}(\hat{H}(1), \mathbf{t}(\lambda))}{(f_i^i + \dots) - (f_a^a + \dots)}. \quad (\text{A12})$$